

EVOLUTION OF THE CORRUPTION IN INDIA

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Abstract

Corruption is a major difficulty that every country of the world is facing. India being the largest democracy in the world and sub-continent in Asia, is a great nation with multi-dimensional complexities intertwined with multi-religious, multi-lingual, multi-cultural masses. The idea of welfare state was given added significance by the framers of the fundamental law of the land. Today millions of the people in India continue to live in an incalculable suffering stalked in extreme poverty, vast gulf of differences and disparities amongst the rich and poor, which lead to a large number of men, women and children leading a life of destitution, misery and pity. Corruption is considered to be the greatest obstacle in the way towards progress for developing country like India. This article deals with the evolution of the corruption in India.

Key words: *Corruption, Evolution and India.*

Introduction

As has rightly been said that everything in the world has its own existence and history and so is the corruption. Anything with its history signifies its presence in different ages. Corruption is one such word that has been practiced in different ages and in all regions of the world. Although India with its versatility and cultural, attitudinal differences, there was absolutely no concern for corruption and it seems to have a recent origin but we can trace back to the ancient period.

Corruption when defined in words involves the improper and dishonest behavior of the persons. This relates with the utter displeasure of the given then enriching themselves by misusing power vested with them. The other words can say that the corruption is the misuse of public authority for individual growth. It is one such outline of behavior that diverges from ethics, morality, tradition, law and civil virtue. The term corruption, on one side cannot be properly defined and on the other side it has its many forms. No single, comprehensive and universally accepted definition. The definition has its own varied versatility and types with respective people, authors and institutes.

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ancient period from 321 BC to 300 BC for the same. The Arthashastra¹, Kautiliya was the chief minister to the king in ancient India, circa 300 BC-1500 states that “the king shall protect trade routes from harassment by courtier state officials, thieves and frontier officers shall make good what is lost. It is impossible for one dealing with government funds not to taste at least a little bit of the king’s wealth”. A very well known king from the medieval period, Kautilya guided the employees for not to be involved in the corruption and the proper role of the state to avoid it fully.

In the era of King Ashoka, his famous Kalinga war and conversion to Buddhism might have prevailed corruption on a lower scale. One more reason behind lowering down of the corruption in the medieval period was, only few authorities were designated for the collection of taxes. But as and when during the time period, Britishers started ruling India, with them, also the bribing started which was not only accepted by Indian officials but by highly placed British officials too.

Leaders in freedom struggle for independence and their true dedication towards getting the independence helped those top politicians of that era, in following & ruling the government honestly that too for about one & half decades. After 3rd and 4th general election, the new political elite lost people’s confidence of being honest. We all being literate can make out as of now, at the central and state level, there are few ministers with corrupt images. Thus, corruption in India, acclaimed as a land of seers, sages and saints and high moral values of truth, honesty and integrity².

Conclusion:

India has been a one among the developing countries where the dilemma of corruption is a major issue because foremost is, it is affecting the economic policies and development, secondly the well-being of people. So it is must for the people living to be well aware of the immorality behind the corrupt consequences. From last few years, as the media got technically sound, has brought this issue of corruption to centre stage for the common people and these people have also supported the battle against corruption. Wherein the faith for core values of equity, justice, democracy and secularism are kept safe.

We can say that, ‘it’ is like a chameleonic character, the corruption has been only changing the colour or the form from the ages we are not even aware of the formation of human society

¹ Manoj Kumar, controlling corruption in International business: Recent UN initiatives, Volume xxv March-December 2001, Cochin university law review, p 256.

² Vidya Bhushan & D.R.Sachdeva, Text of Sociology, Kitab Publication, First reprint edition 2006 p 467.

but having the existence. Almost all major religions of the world, moral and legal school of thought regulated the conduct of mankind and condemn the practice of corruption.

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